

Quality of The Problem Lesson, Its Goals and Objectives

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Abstract:

In this article we are talking about the quality of problem-based learning, the right choice of goals and objectives, the content, form, method, technology and tools of problematic lessons, as well as the involvement of students in the development of educational materials on this process.

Keywords: education, knowledge, skill, skills, problematic learning, pedagogical technology, method, lesson, problematic situation, cooperation, interactive method, form, technique, independent thinking, creative ability, professional quality, research,

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Introduction

The quality of the problem depends largely on the correct selection of its objectives and objectives, content, form, method, technology and tools, as well as the involvement of learners in learning materials to collaborate. Each lesson should be aimed at developing students' knowledge, skills and abilities, and independently finding the information they need from textbooks, manuals and supplementary literature.

The quality of the lesson is dictated by the teacher's responsive approach to the topics being read and analyzed, his ability to convey the content of these topics to his students, and his methodological activities to organize the lessons according to the needs of today. If a teacher can explain the relevance of the ideas to logic, their relevance to the theory, and the logical connection of ideas. It is important to cover the subject based on the possibilities and methods of pedagogical technology.

In particular, the use of teaching technology such as problem-solving, design and heuristics involves teaching students to think creatively and independently, enhancing their independence, building confidence in their abilities, and developing a sense of responsibility. These technologies provide the basis for students to complete the tasks and to master the learning materials. In order to use these technologies in groups, and in small groups, the teacher should understand the purpose of each method and design ways of using problem-solving tasks.

Today's challenges call for a new approach to improving the quality of the problematic lesson, not just the work being done, but the continuous improvement, the development and implementation of new methods and forms. In particular, the main task is to integrate all the subjects taught in general secondary schools, including class 5, with new problems, tasks, tasks [1].

For each subject: defining the logical structure of the course, adapting it to the needs of life, creating problem-based tasks, developing methodological recommendations and instructions based on them, applying the problem-based technology of teaching, experimenting with the results. to develop skills, knowledge, and skills. In this regard, in order to raise the quality of the lessons to a new level, we believe that it is necessary: to organize classes on the basis of all the subjects taught, including computer science, and to recognize internationally recognized innovations in technology and technology in the preparation of problem tasks; reflection of the essence and content of the new generation of literature published in different directions.

Modern teaching requires not only the methods and forms of teaching, but also the implementation of educational, developmental goals, and the collaboration of teachers and students. The nature of the lessons depends on the creativity and professionalism of the teachers.

We believe that to determine the most effective way of doing things, it is important to organize: appropriate problem-solving lessons, taking into account the young and individual capabilities of learners, choosing problem forms, updating student activities, using the time effectively, gradually increase.

The purposeful, convenient and practical form of solving educational problems is to provide the students with the state educational standards, syllabus and textbooks, with a specific goal and objectives, aimed at teaching and nurturing them in order to enable them to work effectively. , educational and methodical manuals, didactic materials, non-traditional pedagogical methods, methods, teaching, information and communication technologies. n process, which by the nature of human experience, knowledge, skills and skills to the younger generation, which is the purpose, content, methods, principles, organizational forms and structural parts of the type shown together.

The main objectives and objectives of the problem lesson are:

atish Focus on identifying goals and objectives;

- establishing effective cooperation between teachers and students;

- use of advanced pedagogical technologies and interactive methods based on them;

- improvement of the results evaluation system;

- the creation and implementation of all its forms, taking into account the latest technical and technological achievements;

- Formation of students' independent thinking, creative abilities and professional qualities in accordance with the requirements of the time;

- Creating a close and lasting link between classes and unconventional reading and research;

- independently collect the necessary information, identify problems, find solutions;

- to critically analyze the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities and apply them in solving new problems;

- Creation of a complex system of training, including organizational, psychological and pedagogical, educational and methodical, information, logistical support;

- Identification of convenient ways and means of finding necessary information, effective use of information resources;

- Determine the most important decision of the assignment, prepare and process the results, systematic and creative approach to the tasks.

It is important to note that without a clear objective of the problem lesson it is impossible to achieve an effective result, and without a specific goal, it is impossible to achieve the set objectives and achieve practical results. The result will be the same as the goal. Only when a teacher sets a clear goal for himself is to look for ways to achieve it. Analysis of needs and objectives in setting goals, focusing on critical issues, setting serious and realistic goals, formulating goals for achieving them, setting motivation goals, focusing on student awareness of goals, and ensuring that each lesson's purpose is aligned with the program's objectives. is required.

In order to formulate the problem lesson objectives according to these requirements, the teacher should know what to take at the end of the lesson and what indicators should be used to achieve the result. Today, there are many disadvantages in defining goals, including: excess of goals, incompatibility with the scale of training resources, formalism in setting goals, frequent shifts in goals during the lesson, and inaccuracies in their formulation.

In setting the goal, the teacher analyzes the curriculum, textbooks, manuals and required literature. It restructures the learning materials, chooses them according to the objectives of the topic. The ability of students to take into account the requirements of an individual approach to education. He selects theoretical and practical material appropriate to the degree of mastering of the sciences [2].

We propose the following algorithm for targeting the problem lesson: to assess the existing problems and identify the main ones, and to formulate these problems accurately. to identify the stages and sequence of their solution, to clearly form intermediate results for each step, to evaluate which of these steps can be implemented accurately in the course of the lesson, and then formulate the specific goal of the lesson.

The problematic lesson should be a prerequisite for students' learning, intellectual development, their activeness, independent thinking, mastering the subject, and directing creative research. The scientific validity of the lesson, the clarity of the topics covered, the role of modern science, as well as the interconnectedness of the sciences and the presence of problematic situations should provide students with a solid knowledge of science [3].

However, analyzes and observations reveal that schools have disadvantages and problems in this regard: teachers do not feel the importance of improving their pedagogical skills, superficial attitude to the scientific process, the relevance of time, living and practice, and previous knowledge of teaching; insufficient account of life experience, their knowledge on new topics, enough to give original information ineffective use of technical means of teaching, e-textbooks and other materials, poor choice of working methods, poor knowledge of the personality and the group, the same training, insufficient attention to the content of the learning material, the inability to apply theoretical knowledge gained in practice; development of research on the problems of inadequate professional competence in schools, lack of competition, and organization of lessons; lack of application of the results in the learning process, etc.

Students face a variety of challenges in preparing and organizing the lesson, which certainly prevents them from improving the process. This is mainly due to the inability to clearly articulate the purpose of the lesson, the uncertainty of what students need to form and develop new concepts, the implementation of educational tasks, and the choice of learning tools to equip the lesson.

As a result of our analysis, we have identified the following common problems and shortcomings in the organization of current lessons: no comparative analysis between disciplines, no consideration of modern education requirements, no use of new laws and

regulations, no conclusions after each lesson. , absence of problematic questions and tasks, how to apply information and pedagogical technologies to this process, to use websites lack of policy and use of official statistical data on socio-economic indicators of the republic, low attention to the adherence to the principles of interdisciplinary continuity and continuity, the latest advances in science, science, technology and technology.

This causes insufficient level of knowledge and skills of students and lags behind the development of science programs. In order to eliminate them, well-known scholars of the Republic are trying to use scientifically based, problem-based teaching technologies, which are adapted to the socio-pedagogical conditions of the region, and to integrate them into the educational process.

Expanding the implementation of these technologies in the classroom process, learning and implementing best international practices in this area, drawing up and implementing specific plans for each subject, including computer science, downloading textbooks, manuals, programs and lectures to electronic disks. it is important to ensure that every student is provided with adequate information and resources [4].

Therefore, in order to contribute to the economic and social development of the country, it is necessary to organize students on the basis of their vocational training and the integration of labor into production. To do this is to organize problem-solving in the classroom, to pay sufficient attention to designing, including the scientific approach to the main types of the process, to learn about its form and size, to create a system for the proper and effective planning of problem lessons, and It is important to engage in research, develop and implement other activities that enhance the quality and effectiveness of the lessons.

Positive resolution of the abovementioned issues in the course of the lesson largely depends on the professionalism, skills, level, preparation and dedication of teachers, and their attitude to the work of teaching and educating the younger generation.

The problematic lesson and the organization of all of these forms are mainly due to some difficulties in the early stages of learning. Grade 5 students, in particular, find it difficult to adapt to new forms of computer science and new requirements. They hardly know how to organize their own activities independently. They will have a problem with which source, how to find, analyze, isolate and organize the basics, express their ideas clearly and clearly, allocate their time, and properly evaluate them. Therefore, each teacher must first of all build confidence in their abilities and mental abilities and patiently teach them how to properly organize their knowledge. It should be able to anticipate and address the problems that arise

during this process, to identify and evaluate student achievement in learning the objectives and tasks of the lesson, to identify the causes of their low results, and to find solutions.

The current system of organizing classes is not able to adequately develop students' thinking abilities, their knowledge needs, and their interest in science. It is important to note that each problem lesson can be successfully implemented in practice, meeting the relevant didactic goals and criteria in a timely manner. At the same time, it is important to consider the ways in which lectures and seminars based on traditional educational technologies can be improved in a timely manner without sacrificing the value and value of the workshop sessions.

The foregoing features of pedagogy, including problem-based teaching, help to understand the nature of technology and the need to incorporate it into the learning process, with a proper assessment.

Thus, all efforts at schools, including troubled lessons, are aimed at preparing students for vocational training, to bring up capable individuals who are able to fully realize their talents and talents. Such works, which are giving their results today, will ensure the further development of the country and the further improvement of the wellbeing of our country. For this purpose it is necessary to carry out tasks for defining the purposes and tasks of problem lessons, use of pedagogical, information, problem-solving technologies in organization of lessons. This, in turn, will increase the efficiency of the process.

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